

Documentation of time-agnostic-library

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Time-agnostic-library is a Python ≥ 3.7 library to perform time-traversal queries on RDF datasets compliant with the OCDM v2.0.1 provenance specification [2]. It is available open source on GitHub under an ISC License [4], and it is distributed as a package that can be installed with pip via a terminal command. Test-Driven Development (TDD) was adopted as a software development process [1].

This document is a high-level description of time-agnostic-library, helpful to understand its structure and operation. First, the modules are introduced, along with viable configuration parameters. Then, the user-oriented methods are described.

The Time Agnostic library is composed of five modules:

- `agnostic_entity`, where the `AgnosticEntity` class is defined, that is the resource to materialize one or all versions based on the available provenance snapshots.
- `agnostic_query`, where the `AgnosticQuery` class is introduced, which represents a generic time-traversal query. `VersionQuery` and `DeltaQuery` inherit from it to perform searches on versions and deltas.
- `prov_entity`. The `ProvEntity` class defines all the change-tracking properties according to the OpenCitations Data Model.
- `sparql`. The `Sparql` class handles SPARQL queries. In particular, it searches on data or change-tracking metadata on the correct dataset in case information is stored on different sources. If there is more than one dataset, it queries each one, returning a single result. Finally, it allows querying both files and triplestores.
- `support`. It contains the `empty_the_cache` method, which frees the cache, and other private methods that are only useful for testing purposes.

Figure 1 shows a UML diagram of all the Python classes implemented in time-agnostic-library. Properties and methods exposed to the user are reported for each object and marked with a plus sign, while private ones are omitted.

Exceptions are the more significant `Sparql` and `ProvEntity`'s ones, meaningful to have a general view of the classes' hierarchy and labeled with a minus sign. For the same purpose, dependence relationships are graphically clarified with a dashed arrow and inheritance with an empty-tipped solid arrow. Notably, all the top classes depend on `ProvEntity`, that is, on the OpenCitations' provenance model. In addition, `AgnosticEntity` and `AgnosticQuery`, which represent materialization and time-traversal queries respectively, depend on `Sparql`, which manages communication with data and provenance collections.

Figure 1: The UML class diagram of all the Python classes implemented in the time-agnostic-library.

Each of these classes works on the assumption that there are a dataset and some provenance. The files' location or the triplestore endpoint where that information resides is provided via a configuration file in JSON format, according to the pattern in Listing 1. In the most straightforward cases, everything is within the same source, whose position should be indicated both under the **dataset** and **provenance** headings. However, the library supports separate and multiple datasets and provenance sources, be they files or triplestores. In addition, it is possible to use mixed sources typologies for both the dataset and the provenance.

Furthermore, some optional values can be set to make executions faster and more efficient, especially regarding queries where the subject URI is unknown. Such queries take advantage of text indexes. Time-agnostic-library supports the text indexes made available by Blazegraph, GraphDB, Fuseki, and Virtuoso. If one of these triplestores was used and a textual index was built, an affirmative boolean value must be set in the related field to take advantage of this feature. As for GraphDB, the name of the connector must be specified.

To conclude the discussion on the configuration file's optional parameters,

`cache_triplestore_url` enables to specify the read and update endpoints of a triplestore to use as a cache. The benefits are at least three:

1. All past reconstructed graphs are saved on triplestore and never on RAM. Then, the impact of the process on the RAM is knocked down.
2. Time-traversal queries are executed on the cache triplestore and not on graphs saved in RAM. Therefore, they are faster.
3. If a query is launched a second time, the already recovered entities' history is not reconstructed but derived from the cache.

However, the cache also has two disadvantages. First, it takes up space. Secondly, the current implementation does not speed the relevant entities' discovery. The variables must be solved each time. If there are isolated triple patterns, for example, all deltas must be queried every time.

```

# TEMPLATE
{
  "dataset": {
    "triplestore_urls": ["TRIPLESTORE_URL_1", "TRIPLESTORE_URL_2",
      → "TRIPLESTORE_URL_N"],
    "file_paths": ["PATH_1", "PATH_2", "PATH_N"]
  },
  "provenance": {
    "triplestore_urls": ["TRIPLESTORE_URL_1", "TRIPLESTORE_URL_2",
      → "TRIPLESTORE_URL_N"],
    "file_paths": ["PATH_1", "PATH_2", "PATH_N"]
  },
  "blazegraph_full_text_search": "no",
  "fuseki_full_text_search": "no",
  "virtuoso_full_text_search": "no",
  "graphdb_connector_name": "GRAPHDB_CONNECTOR_NAME",
  "cache_triplestore_url": {
    "endpoint": "READ_ENDPOINT",
    "update_endpoint": "UPDATE_ENDPOINT"
  }
}

# USAGE EXAMPLE
{
  "dataset": {
    "triplestore_urls": ["http://localhost:9999/blazegraph/sparql"],
    "file_paths": []
  },
  "provenance": {
    "triplestore_urls": [],
    "file_paths": ["/provenance.json"],
  },
  "blazegraph_full_text_search": "yes",
  "fuseki_full_text_search": "no",
  "virtuoso_full_text_search": "no",
  "graphdb_connector_name": "",
  "cache_triplestore_url": {
    "endpoint": "http://localhost:19999/blazegraph/sparql",
    "update_endpoint": "http://localhost:19999/blazegraph/sparql"
  }
}

```

Listing 1: Configuration file's template and usage example.

In order to materialize a version, an instance of the `AgnosticEntity` class must be created, passing an entity URI and the configuration file's path as arguments. The latter parameter, in this as in the following constructors, is optional. The default value is a JSON file named `config.json` in the same directory from which the script was launched. Finally, the `get_state_at_time`

method ought to be run, providing a time of interest and, if provenance metadata is needed, `True` to the `include_prov_metadata` field (Listing 2).

```
# TEMPLATE
agnostic_entity = AgnosticEntity(res=RES_URI, config_path=CONFIG_PATH)
output = agnostic_entity.get_state_at_time(time=(START, END),
↪ include_prov_metadata=BOOL)

# USAGE EXAMPLE
agnostic_entity =
↪ AgnosticEntity(res="https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178",
↪ config_path="./config.json")
output = agnostic_entity.get_state_at_time(time=("2021-10-13", None),
↪ include_prov_metadata=True)
```

Listing 2: Template to materialize an entity’s version and usage example.

The specified time is a tuple in the format `(START, END)`. If one of the two values is `None`, only the other is considered. Time can be specified using any format included in the ISO 8601 subset defined in the W3C note *Date and Time Formats* [5].

The `get_state_at_time` output is always a tuple of three elements: the first is a dictionary that associates graphs and timestamps within the specified interval; the second contains the metadata of the snapshot that were returned; the third is a dictionary including the other snapshots’ provenance metadata if `include_prov_metadata` is `True`, `None` if `False`. More specifically, the `rdflib` library was employed to represent and manipulate graphs, and resources versions in the first dictionary are returned as `rdflib.ConjunctiveGraph` [3].

Listing 3 illustrates the output template and the concrete result of the execution in Listing 2. As can be observed, after October 13, 2021, there is only one snapshot, the status of which was reconstructed and returned into the first dictionary. That snapshot is `<id/80178/prov/se/2>`, whose metadata is contained in the second output dictionary. Finally, the metadata of the other existing snapshot, `<id/80178/prov/se/1>`, is reported in the third dictionary so that the user knows of its presence and, if interested in including it, increases the input interval.

```

# TEMPLATE
(
  {
    TIME_1: ENTITY_CONJUNCTIVE_GRAPH_AT_TIME_1,
    TIME_2: ENTITY_CONJUNCTIVE_GRAPH_AT_TIME_2
  },
  {
    SNAPSHOT_URI_AT_TIME_1: {
      "generatedAtTime": TIME_1,
      "wasAttributedTo": CONTRIBUTION,
      "hadPrimarySource": PRIMARY_SOURCE
    },
    SNAPSHOT_URI_AT_TIME_2: {
      "generatedAtTime": TIME_2,
      "wasAttributedTo": CONTRIBUTION,
      "hadPrimarySource": PRIMARY_SOURCE
    }
  },
  {
    OTHER_SNAPSHOT_URI: {
      "generatedAtTime": GENERATION_TIME,
      "wasAttributedTo": CONTRIBUTION,
      "hadPrimarySource": PRIMARY_SOURCE
    }
  }
)

# CONCRETE EXAMPLE
(
  {
    "2021-10-19T19:55:55": <Graph
    ↪ identifier=N7dbca928e17a4e89a5ca11f198af1b78 (<class
    ↪ rdflib.graph.ConjunctiveGraph>>
  },
  {
    ↪ "https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178/prov/se/2":
    ↪ {
      "generatedAtTime": "2021-10-19T19:55:55",
      "wasAttributedTo":
      ↪ "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8420-0696",
      "hadPrimarySource": None
    }
  },
  {
    ↪ "https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178/prov/se/1":
    ↪ {
      "generatedAtTime": "2021-10-10T23:44:45",
      "wasAttributedTo": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8420-0696",
      "hadPrimarySource":
      ↪ "https://api.crossref.org/works/10.1007/s11192-019-03265-y"
    }
  }
)

```

Listing 3: Output template of the `get_state_at_time` method and concrete example.

On the other hand, if the whole history of a resource is required, the `get_history` method should be run (Listing 4). The class and the parameters are the same as `get_state_at_time` ones, but no interval is indicated because all times are needed.

```
# TEMPLATE
agnostic_entity = AgnosticEntity(res=RES_URI, config_path=CONFIG_PATH)
output = agnostic_entity.get_history(include_prov_metadata=BOOL)

# USAGE EXAMPLE
agnostic_entity =
↪ AgnosticEntity(res="https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178",
↪ config_path="./config.json")
output = agnostic_entity.get_history(include_prov_metadata=True)
```

Listing 4: Output template of the `get_state_at_time` method and concrete example.

The output is different too and is always a two-element tuple. The first is a dictionary containing all the versions of a given resource. The second is a dictionary containing all the provenance metadata linked to that resource if `include_prov_metadata` is `True`, `None` if `False`. Again, the entity's states are represented as `rdflib.ConjunctiveGraph`. Listing 5 shows the output format, along with the outcome of the sample materialization in Listing 4.

```

# TEMPLATE
(
  {
    RES_URI: {
      TIME_1: ENTITY_GRAPH_AT_TIME_1,
      TIME_2: ENTITY_GRAPH_AT_TIME_2
    }
  },
  {
    RES_URI: {
      SNAPSHOT_URI_AT_TIME_1: {
        "generatedAtTime": GENERATION_TIME,
        "wasAttributedTo": CONTRIBUTION,
        "hadPrimarySource": PRIMARY_SOURCE
      },
      SNAPSHOT_URI_AT_TIME_2: {
        "generatedAtTime": GENERATION_TIME,
        "wasAttributedTo": CONTRIBUTION,
        "hadPrimarySource": PRIMARY_SOURCE
      }
    }
  }
)

# CONCRETE EXAMPLE
(
  {
    ↪ "https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178":
    ↪ {
      "2021-10-10T23:44:45": <Graph
      ↪ identifier=Nf560f20d1ad0426fa497d7870f7121b6 (<class
      ↪ rdflib.graph.ConjunctiveGraph>>,
      "2021-10-19T19:55:55": <Graph
      ↪ identifier=Nf560f20d1ad0426fa497d7870f7121b1b6 (<class
      ↪ rdflib.graph.ConjunctiveGraph>>
    }
  },
  {
    ↪ "https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178/prov/se/1":
    ↪ {
      "generatedAtTime": "2021-10-10T23:44:45",
      "wasAttributedTo": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8420-0696",
      "hadPrimarySource":
      ↪ "https://api.crossref.org/works/10.1007/s11192-019-03265-y"
    },
    ↪ "https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178/prov/se/2":
    ↪ {
      "generatedAtTime": "2021-10-19T19:55:55",
      "wasAttributedTo": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8420-0696",
      "hadPrimarySource": None
    }
  }
)

```

Listing 5: Output template of the `get_history` method and concrete example.

Using a dictionary for the first output element may seem unnecessary since it consists of only one key. In reality, `AgnosticEntity` has an optional parameter, `related_entities_history`. If it is set to `True`, the `get_history` function returns the history of the entity indicated in the `res` field and all related ones. One resource is related to another when linked by an incoming connection rather than an outgoing one. In this case, the first element of the output tuple turns out to be a dictionary of as many keys as there are related entities plus the entity itself.

Proceeding, the `VersionQuery` class must be instantiated to make a single-version structured query, passing as an argument a SPARQL query string, a tuple representing the interval of interest, and the configuration file's path. It should be noted that the library only supports `SELECT` searches; therefore, `CONSTRUCT`, `ASK` or `DESCRIBE` searches are not allowed. Ultimately, the `run_agnostic_query` method ought to be executed (Listing 6).

```
# TEMPLATE
agnostic_query = VersionQuery(query=QUERY_STRING, on_time=(START, END),
↪ config_path=CONFIG_PATH)
output = agnostic_query.run_agnostic_query()

# USAGE EXAMPLE
query = """
PREFIX literal:
↪ <http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/>
SELECT ?id ?literal
WHERE {
    ?id literal:hasLiteralValue ?literal.
    FILTER REGEX(?literal, "\.?$")
}
"""
agnostic_query = VersionQuery(query, ("2021-10-13", None),
↪ "./config.json")
output = agnostic_query.run_agnostic_query()
```

Listing 6: Code template to perform a single-version structured query and usage example.

In the example of Listing 6, there is a triple with an unknown subject. In that event, it is necessary to narrow the field by textual searches on deltas, which can be faster if Blazegraph, GraphDB, Fuseki, or Virtuoso were used as a triplestore, a textual index was reconstructed, and a positive boolean value was passed in the related configuration field.

The output is a dictionary where the keys are the snapshots relevant to that query within the input interval. The values correspond to sets of tuples containing the query results at the time specified by the key. The positional value of the elements in the tuples is equivalent to the variables indicated in the query. Listing 7 details the output template and the concrete output of the

execution in Listing 6. As it can be noted, a version no longer existing of the literal value was correctly returned, proving that the query was executed on a past state of the resource.

```
# TEMPLATE
{
  TIME: {
    (VALUE_1_OF_VARIABLE_1, VALUE_1_OF_VARIABLE_2,
     ↪ VALUE_1_OF_VARIABLE_N),
    (VALUE_2_OF_VARIABLE_1, VALUE_2_OF_VARIABLE_2,
     ↪ VALUE_2_OF_VARIABLE_N),
    (VALUE_N_OF_VARIABLE_1, VALUE_N_OF_VARIABLE_2,
     ↪ VALUE_N_OF_VARIABLE_N)
  }
}

# CONCRETE EXAMPLE
{'2021-10-10T23:44:45':
 ↪ {'https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178',
 ↪  '10.1111/j.1365-2648.2012.06023.x.'}}
```

Listing 7: Output template of a single-version structured query and concrete example.

On the other hand, if a cross-version structured query is needed, it is sufficient to specify no time. It is worth pointing out that the output of a cross-version structured query does not report all the dataset’s snapshots but only those relevant to each of the resources involved in the query at each time. For example, Listing 8 shows a query on all literal values `<id/80178>` has had over time. Its output correctly reports that such id had value “10.1111/j.1365 2648.2012.06023.x.” from 10 October at 23:44:45 to 19 October 2021 at 19:55:55, when the trailing point was removed. Therefore, exclusively the times when something happened to `<id/80178>`, not to any dataset’s entity, are returned.

```

query = """
PREFIX literal:
↪ <http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/>
SELECT DISTINCT ?value
WHERE {
    <https://github.com/opencitations/time_agnostic_library/id/80178>
    literal:hasLiteralValue ?value.
}
"""
agnostic_query = VersionQuery(query, config_path="./config.json")
output = agnostic_query.run_agnostic_query()

# output = {
#     '2021-10-10T23:44:45': {('10.1111/j.1365-2648.2012.06023.x',)},
#     '2021-10-19T19:55:55': {('10.1111/j.1365-2648.2012.06023.x',)}
# }

```

Listing 8: Example of a cross-version structured query and related output.

Then, the `DeltaQuery` class must be instantiated to perform a query on deltas, passing a SPARQL query string, a set of properties, and the configuration file's path as arguments. The query string is helpful to identify the entities whose changes need to be investigated. Again, only `SELECT` searches are allowed. At the same time, the predicates set narrows the field to those resources where the properties specified in the set have changed. If no property was indicated, any changes are considered. In addition, it is possible to input a time in the form of a tuple, with the same possibilities already described regarding version materialization. In that event, the query is executed on the specified range, otherwise on all dataset's changes. Lastly, the `run_agnostic_query` method should be launched on the instantiated object, as shown in Listing 9. All identifiers are searched in the corresponding usage example where the property `<http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/>` was modified after 13 October 2021.

```

# TEMPLATE
agnostic_entity = DeltaQuery(query=QUERY_STRING, on_time=(START, END),
↪ changed_properties=PROPERTIES_SET, config_path=CONFIG_PATH)
output = agnostic_entity.run_agnostic_query()

# USAGE EXAMPLE
query = """
PREFIX datacite: <http://purl.org/spar/datacite/>
SELECT DISTINCT ?id
WHERE {
    ?id a datacite:Identifier.
}
"""
agnostic_entity = DeltaQuery(query=query, on_time=("2021-10-13", None),
↪ changed_properties={"http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/"},
↪ config_path="./config.json")
output = agnostic_entity.run_agnostic_query()

```

Listing 9: Code template to perform a single-delta structured query and usage example. Cross-delta structured queries only differ because the `on_time` field is equal to `None`.

The output is a dictionary that reports the modified entities, when they were created, modified, and deleted, following the format in Listing 10. Changes are reported as SPARQL update queries, in the same way as deltas are stored according to the OpenCitations Data Model. Merges are exceptions because they cannot be expressed in SPARQL: in that case, a description is given in a human-readable format that specifies which resources were merged. If the entity was not created or deleted within the indicated range, the `created` or `deleted` value is `None`. On the other hand, if the entity does not exist within the input interval, the `modified` value is an empty dictionary. It is essential to record creation and deletion dates separately from the changes not to be lost. Indeed, the creation snapshot has no delta and would not appear among the changes, just as it is impossible to understand from a diff if a resource was deleted because the output does not report the entirety of the resource.

The example in Listing 10 reports the output of the query in Listing 9. It shows that the identifier associated with the URI `<id/80178>` was created on 10 October 2021 at 23:44:45 and still exists in the data collection, as no cancellation date is indicated. In addition, it was modified on 19 October 2021 at 19:55:55, removing the trailing point.

```

# TEMPLATE
{
  RES_URI_1: {
    "created": TIMESTAMP_CREATION,
    "modified": {
      TIMESTAMP_1: UPDATE_QUERY_1,
      TIMESTAMP_2: UPDATE_QUERY_2,
      TIMESTAMP_N: UPDATE_QUERY_N
    },
    "deleted": TIMESTAMP_DELETION
  },
  RES_URI_N: {
    "created": TIMESTAMP_CREATION,
    "modified": {
      TIMESTAMP_1: UPDATE_QUERY_1,
      TIMESTAMP_2: UPDATE_QUERY_2,
      TIMESTAMP_N: UPDATE_QUERY_N
    },
    "deleted": TIMESTAMP_DELETION
  }
}

# CONCRETE EXAMPLE
{
  "https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178": {
    "created": "2021-10-10T23:44:45",
    "modified": {
      "2021-10-19T19:55:55": "DELETE DATA { GRAPH
↪ <https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/>
↪ {
↪ <https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178>
↪ <http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/hasLiteralValue>
↪ '10.1111/j.1365-2648.2012.06023.x.' . } }"; INSERT DATA {
↪ GRAPH
↪ <https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/>
↪ {
↪ <https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/id/80178>
↪ <http://www.essepuntato.it/2010/06/literalreification/hasLiteralValue>
↪ '10.1111/j.1365-2648.2012.06023.x.' . } }"
    },
    "deleted": None
  }
}

```

Listing 10: Output template of a structured query on changes, along with a concrete example.

0.1 Cache system

The last module exposed to the user is *support*, which provides the `empty_the_cache` function to free the cache triplestore. In order to use it, it is sufficient to pass as a parameter the path of the configuration file, as shown in Listing 11.

```
# TEMPLATE
empty_the_cache(config_path = CONFIG_PATH)

# USAGE EXAMPLE
empty_the_cache(config_path = "./config.json")
```

Listing 11: Code template to empty the cache and usage example.

The implementation of the cache system relies on a triplestore. A text file would not have been as effective because the cache’s primary objective is to make queries on the past graphs faster after they have been recovered. A text file would have been detrimental to this purpose, lacking the optimizations and indexes that characterize a triplestore. Moreover, the cache triplestore must be separated from both the data and the provenance collections, as transcribed information is incompatible and contradictory with that present on the first two. Indeed, in the cache, statements belonging to different times coexist. Also, the cache system was implemented only to speed up version queries, while it does not affect delta queries, as they do not reconstruct past graphs. Therefore, the only class involved is `VersionQuery`.

Inside the cache, each triple pertains to a named graph, whose URI is `f‘https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/{timestamp}’`, where `{timestamp}` is the value of `prov:generatedAtTime` of the relative provenance snapshot. Such a solution makes the code to run queries on different versions short and efficient. As shown in Listing 12, it cycles on the timestamps relevant for the user’s query, transforming the SPARQL string. In row 5, the string is split to the first occurrence of `WHERE`, ignoring uppercase or lowercase letters. `f‘FROM <https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/{timestamp}>’` is placed before `WHERE`, which is then reset with the rest of the query. In this way, the query is run on a dataset’s portion as it appeared in the time indicated by `timestamp`.

The cache allows quicker searches because it avoids reconstructing the same entities’ histories more than once. If the library only recovered the entire resources’ past, the strategy shown so far would have been adequate. It would have been enough to check if a URI is in the cache before starting the materialization process and, if it exists, skip it. However, `time-agnostic-library` also stores portions of the past via single-version-structured queries in the cache. Therefore, confirming the presence of a URI in the cache is not sufficient because this URI could be in another temporal graph, which is not of current

```

1 def run_agnostic_query(self) -> Dict[str, Set[Tuple]]:
2     # [...]
3     if self.cache_triplestore_url:
4         for timestamp, _ in self.relevant_graphs.items():
5             split_by_where = re.split(pattern="where", string=self.query,
6                 ↪ maxsplit=1, flags=re.IGNORECASE)
7             query_named_graph = split_by_where[0] + f"FROM
8                 ↪ <https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/{timestamp}>
9                 ↪ WHERE" + split_by_where[1]
10
11     [...]

```

Listing 12: Snippet code to run a query on a named graph in the cache triplestore.

interest.

In order to overcome this limitation, when a cross-version structured query is run, the function `_cache_entity_graph` updates the cache triplestore with the statement

```

<{entity}/entity>
<https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/isComplete>
f“‘true’”, where {entity} is the URI of a relevant entity involved in the time-
traversal query.

```

Instead, when a single-version query is executed, information about the start time and end time is saved in the cache via `<{entity}/entity>`
`<https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/hasStartingDate>`
`f“‘{starting_date}’”` and `<{entity}/entity>`
`<https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/hasEndingDate>`
`f“‘{ending_date}’”`.

When a search is executed a second time, the method `_get_relevant_timestamps_from_cache` looks for every involved entity if `?complete` results equal to `‘true’` or if the required interval is within the cached interval. If one of those two conditions holds, the relevant timestamps are saved to be used in `run_agnostic_query`, as shown in Listing 12, and the reconstruction can be skipped.

In order to identify the relevant times, another problem must be solved. In fact, the cache stores not only restored graphs but also aligned and duplicated ones. If a resource was not modified between a snapshot and the next one, its graph is cloned. In order to mark an original snapshot, its URI is saved in a triple that connects it to the reference entity via `<http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#specializationOf>`. Ultimately, by searching for URIs linked via that predicate, the results are the actual snapshots that were saved. Such triples are included in a separate graph, whose name is `f“https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/relevant/{timestamp}”` so that `run_agnostic_query` does not return unwanted provenance information. Finally, since the generation timestamps are directly con-

tained in the named graph, they can be derived with a simple split.
 The UML diagram in Fig. 2 exemplifies the entire cache system.

Figure 2: UML sequence diagram of the cache system.

References

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